

Women's Access to Health Care in India: Barriers and Government Interventions

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ABSTRACT

Women are regarded as asset of any country. Women health refers to the health issues specific to female anatomy. Women's health is a broad term which refers to physical, mental health problems those are of exclusive concern for women and which are more common in women or which are differ as compared to men. Women's health is defined in the terms of reproductive health and safety for younger women, girls and diseases in their reproductive organs. The poor health conditions of women are due to poor social and economical status as compared to men. Lower status and violence are also responsible for poor health of women. Women face health inequities because of their specific needs around sexual and reproductive health care. All the factors of gender inequity including limited access to education, legal systems that fail to protect women and gender-based violence are exacerbated by poverty. This paper highlights the women health issues, causes of poor health of women. In this paper, focus is also given to barriers coming in the way to women health. The objectives of the paper are to highlight the schemes those are provided by the government for the development and empowerment of women and for the development of children across the country.

Keywords: Patriarchy, Gender Barriers, Reproductive Health, Poor Health, Malnutrition

INTRODUCTION

Women's health refers to the branch of medicine that focuses on the treatment and diagnosis of diseases and conditions that affect a woman's physical and emotional well-being. Health is an important factor that contributes to human wellbeing and economic growth. Indian women have to face number of health issues, which ultimately affect the aggregate economy's output. Addressing the gender, class or ethnic disparities that exist in healthcare and improving the health outcomes can contribute to economic gain through the creation of quality human capital and increased levels

of savings and investment.

Women with a portion to over of half population in the world, especially in developing country like India, should take into consideration any community based mental health programs. In 2011, women and girls remain victims of gender inequality (Read & Gorman, 2010). Women's significant roles in global development of society, child rearing, family endorsement and workplace, their mental health influence by many socio-cultural factors (Navabi-Nejad, 2000). In contrast to women's participation as the paid labor force during the recent decades

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that increased in country too, the major lines of 2 women's psychology investigation has mostly focused to the effects of child care and maternal employment in children rather than their psychic well-being (Khodarahimi, 2005). While universal growing literature has examined the effect of women's multiple roles on their own physical and mental health, and indicated their multiple roles have negative health outcomes for them. Social inequality has damaging consequences for the mental and emotional well-being of women. Throughout their lives, women may be considered "at risk" of developing emotional problems due to a host of social factors. Limited participation in public life, restricted decision-making, devalued role expectations, poverty, violence and sexual abuse undermine the potential for emotional well-being. Social change is needed to strengthen the emotional well-being of women individually and collectively in society. Women are integral to all aspects of society. However the multiple roles that they play in society render them at greater risk of experiencing mental problems than others in the community. Women bear the burden of responsibility associated with being wives, mother and career minders of others. Increasingly, women are becoming an essential part of the labour force and in one quarter to one third of households they are the prime source of 3 income (WHO, 1995). Impoverishment equates not only to hunger and sickness, but also to disempowerment and marginalization. As a result, many women and girls are subject to violence and other human rights abuses. When addressing women's lives, it is crucial to examine the underlying social, cultural,

environmental, epidemiological, and economic determinants of health (Marmot, Friel, Bell, Houweling, & Taylor, 2008). Women and girls have specific health needs, and health systems around the world are failing them (World Health Organization [WHO], 2009). The WHO states that today women's health has become an urgent priority, yet the data surrounding this issue are limited and often unreliable (WHO, 2009).

In India, improving women's access to healthcare is very important for achieving gender equality. It is necessary to take into account the facts; according to the World Gap Report, India now ranks 140th out of 156 Nations in the terms of gender disparity.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The researchers have been adopted descriptive methodology for this study. The Research has been used secondary data sources such as books, journals, newspapers and online database. From which light has been shed on women's health in India. India is a developing country due to which the basic needs of its people are health, education, employment. Basically, India spends a large part of its GDP on health facilities, but despite this, due to the large population of India, they do not benefit. The Government of India has also run many schemes for women which have been mentioned in this paper.

CAUSES OF POOR HEALTH OF WOMEN IN INDIA

Women in India face many issues like malnutrition, poor maternal health, mental health, HIV/AIDS, Breast cancer, urinary problems, obesity, domestic

violence, poverty etc. These issues may vary by geography, socio economic standing and culture. Mainstreaming a gender perspective needs to be coupled with mainstreaming mental health issues as well, because women disproportionately suffer from mental health disorders and are more frequently subject to social causes that lead to mental illness and psychosocial distress. Some causes of poor health in women are as under:

1. Malnutrition: Nutrition plays a major role in an individual's overall health, psychological and physical health status is often dramatically impacted by the presence of malnutrition. Maternal malnutrition has been associated with an increased risk of maternal mortality and also child birth defects. Addressing the issues of malnutrition would have a beneficial outcomes for women and children. India has one of the highest rates of malnourished women among developing countries. A study in 2012 done by Tarozzi have found the nutritional intake of early adolescents to be approximately equal. However, it is seen that the rate of malnutrition increases for women as they enter adulthood

2. Lack of maternal health: The lack of maternal health contributes to the economic disparities of mothers and their children. Poor maternal health not only affects a child's health in adverse ways but also decreases a woman's ability to participate in economic activities. In India women lack of proper maternal health.

3. Gender biasness and suicide: *Gender biasness is a major problem in India. The suicide rate in India is five times higher than that of the developed world. Furthermore, the rate of suicide has been found to be higher in women as compared*

to men in India. It is particularly high among female sex workers in India and in who face numerous forms of discrimination for their gender and line of work. The most common reasons for women's suicide is directly related to: Depression, Gender discrimination, Domestic violence and anxiety etc.

4. Domestic Violence: Domestic violence is a major issue in India. Domestic violence is defined as acts of physical, psychological, and sexual violence against women is found across the world and is currently viewed as a hidden epidemic by the World Health Organization.

As per reports of India National Family Health Survey III (2005-2006), 31 percent of all women reported having been the victims of physical violence in the last 12 months. However, the actual number of victims may be much higher. The study found that the poorest women fared worst among middle and high-income women.

5. Environment: Environmental factors contribute to many diseases in women. Environmental conditions range from water, air, and soil pollution to contamination through the workplace . Occupational hazards include exposure to lead, chemicals, pesticides, tobacco smoke and noise. Home and community environmental factors-from radon, lead-based paints, electromagnetic fields, food, and cosmetics to heatstroke, hypothermia, and violence-affect women's health. The ways in which environmental factors may disrupt women's endocrine, reproductive, central nervous, and immune systems and cause specific diseases such as cancer, autoimmune diseases, endometriosis, and osteoporosis are only beginning to be

understood.

6. Patriarchy and Economic dependency: Women in India take less health care facilities due to patriarchy society. They face dual burden and cannot speak boldly. They have to obey her father, brother, husband and after marriage son. They cannot express their pain. So they face health problems alone. They are dependent upon husbands as income resource. They can not make extra expenses. They face numerous, well-documented barriers to healthcare and limited decision-making powers, household care responsibilities, restrictions on travelling alone, and the prioritization of male family members' health. So women face health problems.

7. Illiteracy and lack of awareness: India is a poor country. So women are poor and illiterate. Women remain busy in their house hold chores and in taking care of their family. They live inside four walls of house. So they are not aware of health facilities. They neglect their health and they do not avail health facilities. Infect they have no time for themselves. They avoid their health care. They are also not aware of HIV/AIDS and STD. They do not use contraceptives while sex. So that is the reason they are caught in serious health issues like breast and cervical cancer also.

8. Priority to family: Women's poor health is caused due habit of giving priority to their family. They are socialized in the environment where they learn to take care of others. They neglect their health. They do not take proper diet. So it is a main cause of their poor health. They often lack adequate resources to pay for care.

BARRIERS PREVENT WOMEN

TO AVAIL HEALTH SERVICES

In India, women face many difficulties to access health facilities. There are many barriers those are as under:

1. Social barriers: Women have to bear gender discrimination and the associated factors of poverty, hunger, malnutrition and overwork. An extreme but common expression of gender inequality is in sexual and domestic violence, perpetrated against women. These forms of socio-cultural violence, contribute to the high prevalence of mental problems experienced by women. The demands of household chores meant that women cannot rest or travel to seek care. Permission and accompaniment from a male partner or household member are required for women to travel. Women also lack family support about their care.

2. Economic barriers: Poverty is an important barrier to positive health outcomes for women, poverty tend to yield a higher burden on women and girl's health. For example, feeding practices (malnutrition) and use of unsafe cooking fuels (COPD) Women cannot necessarily cover the costs of the required journey as they have no income resources. They are dependent upon their family male members for expenses. Hospitals are far away from many areas and these are expensive. Transportation is expensive. Inadequate education, research, and treatment is just one of the many, huge barriers that women face in the healthcare system. Another one being affordability and accessibility.

3. Environmental and structural barriers: A key barrier to health services emphasized in all focus groups are the lack of medical facilities in the village. The existing structure of healthcare

system was described as inadequate to deal with the reported health challenges at the village-level. There is no doctor available in the village. The lack of facilities was also linked to poor individual-level knowledge about health and delayed treatment seeking.

4. Educational and technological barriers: Women lack of education amongst themselves and growing teens and children. It is crucial that growing girls to learn about their bodies; how they work, what is normal and not, basic hygiene, hormones, etc. However, the education system has consistently failed young girls in understanding the importance of sexual education, and accurate physical education. They have no access to technology. So they lag behind in health. Poor access of technology is also a barrier in women health.

5. Cognitive barriers: Lack of information on factors relating to health care or the inability to use such information creates cognitive barriers. Acquiring and using healthcare-related information is limited by illiteracy and by lack of access to many technologies. Migration caused a cognitive barrier in the form of language skills because they did not speak the local languages.

Schemes For The Development Of Women And Children

The various schemes are being run by Government for the development and empowerment of women and for the development of children across the country, including rural areas, are as under:

1. Anganwadi Services: Under Anganwadi Services, a package of six services is provided to Pregnant Women and Lactating Mothers and

to Children under the age of 6 years i.e. Supplementary Nutrition (SNP); Pre-school Non-formal Education; Nutrition & Health Education; Immunization; Health Check-ups and Referral Services. Three of the six services, viz., Immunization, Health check-up and Referral Services are related to health and are provided through NRHM & Public Health Infrastructure.

2. Sakhi One Stop Centre and Universalization of Women Helplines: Women Welfare Division is divided into two schemes from Nirbhaya Fund namely One Stop Centre and Universalization of Women Helplines. The One Stop Centres (OSCs), popularly known as *Sakhi* Centres and they aim to facilitate women affected by violence (including domestic violence) with a range of integrated services under one roof such as Police facilitation, medical aid, providing legal aid and legal counselling, psycho-social counseling and temporary shelter etc. The Women Helpline (WHL) Scheme provides 24 hours emergency and non-emergency response to women affected by violence, both in public and private spaces by linking them with appropriate authority such as Police, One Stop Centre, Hospital, Legal Services etc. WHL also supports women in distress with rescue van and counseling services in addition to providing information about women welfare schemes and programs across the country. Women can dial 181 short code to avail services from this Helpline number.

3. Swadhar Greh Scheme: The

- Swadhar Greh Scheme has been implemented as a Centrally Sponsored Scheme for women who are victims of difficult circumstances in need of institutional support for rehabilitation so that they could lead their life with dignity.
4. **Ujjawala Scheme:** This scheme is centrally sponsored scheme. This scheme prevents from trafficking and for Rescue, Rehabilitation, Re-integration and Repatriation of victims of trafficking for commercial sexual exploitation.
 5. **Working Women Hostel:** Working Women Hostel Scheme is implemented by the Government with main aim is to provide safe and conveniently located accommodation for working women, with day care facility for their children, wherever possible, in urban, semi-urban and even rural areas where employment opportunity for women.
 6. **Scheme for Adolescent Girls (SAG):** This is a Centrally-sponsored scheme which aims at providing nutritional support to out of school girls in the age group of 11-14 years for improving their health and nutritional status under the nutrition component on one hand and motivates them to go back to formal schooling, provides life skill training, accessing public services etc.
 7. **POSHAN Abhiyaan:** POSHAN Abhiyaan was launched on 8th March, 2018. It aims to address malnutrition issues across the nation through components like ICT Application, Convergence, Community Mobility, Behavioural Change & Jan Andolan Capacity Building, Incentive, Awards and Innovations.
 9. **Beti Bachao Beti Padhao (BBBP) :** Beti Bachao Beti Padhao (BBBP) Scheme was launched on 22nd January 2015 with an aim to address declining Child Sex Ratio (CSR) and related issues of empowerment of girls and women over a life cycle continuum. The main objective of the scheme is to prevent gender biasness, to ensure survival and protection of the girl child and to ensure education and participation of the girl child.
 10. **Mahila Shakti Kendra (MSK):** The Mahila Shakti Kendra (MSK) Scheme was approved in November, 2017 as a centrally sponsored scheme to empower rural women through community participation. The aims to empower women. The scheme is implemented through State Governments and UT Administrations with a cost sharing ratio of 60:40 between Centre and States except for North East & Special Category States where the funding ratio is 90:10. For Union Territories 100% central funding is provided.
 11. **Child Protection Services Scheme:** The Ministry is implementing Child Protection Services Scheme under the Mission Vatsalya scheme (erstwhile Integrated Child Protection Scheme) since 2009-10 for supporting the children in difficult circumstances. Under the scheme institutional care is provided through Child Care Institutes (CCIs), as a rehabilitative measure. The programmes and activities in Homes inter-alia include age-appropriate education, access to vocational training, recreation,

health care, counseling etc. Under the non-institutional care component, support is extended for adoption, foster care and sponsorship.

12. **Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana (PMMVY):** It is a Centrally Sponsored Conditional Cash Transfer Scheme, for implementation across the country with effect from 2017. The maternity benefit under PMMVY is available to all Pregnant Women & Lactating Mothers (PW&LM) excluding PW&LM who are in regular employment with the Central Government or the State Governments or Public Sector Undertakings (PSUs) or those who are in receipt of similar benefits under any law for the time being in force, for first living child of family. Under the scheme Rs.5,000/- are provided to the eligible beneficiary in three installments during pregnancy and lactation in response to individual fulfilling certain nutrition and health seeking conditions. The eligible beneficiary also receives the remaining cash incentive as per approved norms towards maternity benefit under Janani Suraksha Yojana (JSY) after institutional delivery so that on an average, a woman gets Rs.6,000/-.

CONCLUSION

Women are the main and important part of a nation. Good primary health care for women is not only vital for promoting economic stability but also critical to limiting costs across the health care system: 90 percent of national health care expenditures should attribute to treating

chronic and mental health conditions, both of which significantly impact adult women. There is a lack of funding, a lack of representation, and a lack of education across the world. Primary care for women has been weakened as our bodily rights become more and more politicized. If we want to improve our healthcare system for all, we need to start with women.

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